

The Potential of Grounded Synthetic Corpora to Address Persistent Geoparsing Challenges

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Abstract

Geoparsing, extracting and geocoding place mentions from text, remains geographically and linguistically uneven, with persistent under-representation of non-English contexts and less prominent places. Manual corpus annotation is prohibitively expensive, and existing automated approaches are limited in their annotation completeness. This paper argues that grounded synthetic corpora, generated by LLMs but anchored in gazetteers and contextual sources such as Wikipedia, offer a scalable complement to human-authored benchmarks. By inverting the conventional workflow through sampling places first, then generating naturalistic text around them toponyms become pre-disambiguated by construction, enabling balanced spatial coverage and multilingual scope. We outline the benefits, identify new bias pathways, and set out the key research challenges for producing gold-standard synthetic corpora that reduce bias without introducing new ones.

Keywords: geoparsing, synthetic corpora, large language models, gazetteers, spatial bias

1. Introduction

Geoparsing, the extraction of place mentions from text and their subsequent disambiguation and geocoding (Hu and Adams 2021; Gritta, Pilehvar, and Collier 2020), has become a foundational capability for many geographic information extraction pipelines, from crisis mapping to spatial humanities (Gelernter and Balaji 2013; Avvenuti et al. 2018; Brunila et al. 2023). Yet despite strong results on well-curated benchmarks, the field is not ‘solved’: multiple studies and community discussions emphasize that geoparser performance remains geographically and linguistically uneven, with strong performance in Europe and the United States and weaker outcomes elsewhere (Liu et al. 2022; Leppämäki, Toivonen, and Hiippala 2024). This imbalance is closely tied to the

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training and evaluation corpora we rely on, which often under-represent less prominent places, non-English contexts, and the diversity of spatial granularities that appear in real-world text. Moreover, high-quality gold-standard corpus creation is labor-intensive. For instance, the annotation of the DLGeoTweet dataset (7,364 tweets) consumed around 1,000 person-hours (X. Hu et al. 2024), which constrains the coverage of new domains, languages, and geographies.

These limitations have direct downstream consequences for GeoAI applications that depend on reliable place grounding, including crisis mapping, public health surveillance, and conflict monitoring. Uneven geoparsing accuracy can systematically degrade situational awareness in underrepresented regions and languages, reinforcing existing geographic blind spots in data-driven decision-making.

This paper argues that grounded synthetic geoparsing corpora, generated with large language models (LLMs) but anchored in gazetteers and contextual sources, offer a route that scales annotation while keeping ground truth verifiable. We explore their **potential** to: (1) reduce the burden of manual annotation, (2) facilitate the training and evaluation of novel geoparsing models, (3) enable the curation of synthetic corpora across a variety of languages, and (4) provide a mechanism to address spatial bias.

We also critically assess the **risks** of this methodology, including: (1) source-coverage bias, (2) LLM bias inheritance and stylistic skew, (3) methodological bias toward certain resolution heuristics, (4) geographic inaccuracies, and (5) evaluation bias.

Finally, we outline **key research challenges** for generating high-quality synthetic corpora for geoparsing: (1) reducing reliance on auxiliary sources for contextual grounding, (2) integrating spatial relationships (e.g., topological, directional, or distance-based) into the curation process, (3) automating the annotation, disambiguation, and geocoding of non-toponym spatial descriptions, (4) quantitatively demonstrating the real-world benefits of synthetic geoparsing corpora, and (5) ensuring the scalability of synthetic corpora generation computationally, linguistically, and geographically.

2. From manual *annotation* to controlled *synthesis*

High-quality geoparsing datasets are crucial for training models and benchmarking techniques, requiring exhaustive annotations for toponym recognition (precision, recall, F1-score) and toponym resolution (disambiguation and geographic mapping, evaluated via Mean/Median Error Distance, AUC, or Accuracy@k). Manual annotation has long been the bottleneck, highlighted by the DLGeoTweet corpus, which required 1,000 person-hours to annotate 7,364 tweets and 12,510 place references (X. Hu et al. 2024). To mitigate this, semi-automated methods emerged, using named entity recognition (NER) or crowdsourcing to pre-identify location mentions, cross-referenced with gazetteers for candidate locations, and leaving annotators to resolve ambiguities (Leidner 2006; DeLozier et al. 2016; Wallgrün et al. 2018; Karimzadeh and MacEachren 2019; X. Hu et al. 2024). Yet, their success depends on NER tool reliability and gazetteer coverage.

Fully automated approaches further reduce manual effort. Gritta et al. (2018) combined GeoNames

and Wikipedia to annotate linked toponyms in article introductions, however missed non-linked mentions, limiting evaluations to accuracy-based metrics. Similarly, Ohno et al. (2024) constructed a large-scale corpus from Wikipedia hyperlinks, annotating article titles and linked locations with coordinates, but excluded non-hyperlinked mentions, resulting in incomplete annotations (Ohno et al. 2024).

Geoparsing corpora have been sourced from diverse text types, such as social media, news, Wikipedia, historical texts, and web pages (Wallgrün et al. 2018; Karimzadeh and MacEachren 2019; X. Hu et al. 2024; Leidner 2006; Gritta, Pilehvar, and Collier 2018, 2020; Leppämäki, Toivonen, and Hiippala 2024; Gritta et al. 2018; Ohno et al. 2024; DeLozier et al. 2016; Katz and Schill 2013). However, most datasets remain English-centric, with only a handful covering languages such as Finnish, Italian, Serbian, Spanish, Dutch, or German (Leppämäki, Toivonen, and Hiippala 2024; Perišić et al. 2022; Molina-Villegas et al. 2021; Ardanuy and Sporleder 2017; Rolwes et al. 2024; Ilyankou et al. 2026). While advances in automation have improved scalability, persistent geographic and linguistic biases (Liu et al. 2022; Leppämäki, Toivonen, and Hiippala 2024) reveal the need for more robust, diverse, and inclusive curation strategies.

The generation of synthetic corpora through LLMs by grounding them in gazetteers and contextual sources offers a new option for addressing these persistent challenges in geoparsing. The central idea is to invert the typical corpus-building workflow (see Fig. 1). Instead of starting from a text collection and then laboriously annotating, disambiguating and geocoding toponyms, we propose starting from a selection of places (e.g. OSM-Gazetteer), retrieve contextual descriptions (e.g. Wikipedia), and then generate short, naturalistic texts that mention those places in diverse styles using LLMs. Because the target places are already known, their spans and ground-truth coordinates can be attached directly during generation, making toponym resolution pre-disambiguated by construction. A pipeline following this principle can be designed to explicitly target balanced spatial coverage, as well as a broad mix of place types and granularities, and a range of languages.

3. Benefits of synthetic corpora for geoparsing

First, synthetic corpora reduce the burden of manual annotation. Gold-standard geoparsing datasets demand extensive labor for curation, but pre-disambiguated toponyms remove the need for exhaustive labelling and annotation. Annotators can spend their time checking generated examples rather than labelling from scratch, significantly reducing the cost and time required to produce high-quality benchmarks.

Second, synthetic corpora facilitate the training and evaluation of novel geoparsing models. Their controlled generation allows the creation of benchmark and training datasets designed to address specific challenges, such as uneven spatial distribution of toponyms, varying granularities, or temporal variations, while the reduction in annotation effort enables the construction of larger datasets. They could also be used in conjunction with real-world datasets to improve model performance in low-resource settings.

Third, it allows the curation of synthetic corpora across a variety of languages, thereby addressing a critical limitation in existing geoparsing resources. Most geoparsing corpora are dom-

Figure 1: Simplified comparison of the workflows of manual geoparsing corpora curation and the controlled synthesis of synthetic corpora.

inated by English, leaving many languages underrepresented or entirely absent from benchmarks. By leveraging LLMs grounded in gazetteers and contextual sources, synthetic corpora can be generated in multiple languages ensuring linguistic diversity.

Finally, and most critically for GeoAI fairness and robustness, **synthetic corpora provide a mechanism to address spatial bias**. By stratifying the selection of places across geographic space, synthetic datasets can avoid over-representing labels in regions already well-covered by existing corpora, fostering more balanced and inclusive evaluations.

4. Risks of synthetic corpora for geoparsing

At the same time, synthetic corpora introduce **distinct risks** that must be made explicit, particularly if the goal is to reduce and not reshuffle bias. We highlight several ‘new bias’ pathways that are especially relevant to geoparsing.

First, synthetic corpora can inherit source-coverage bias: if the pipeline depends on resources such as OpenStreetMap and Wikipedia, then the synthetic corpus inherits their uneven completeness and linkage quality (Acheson, Sabbata, and Purves 2017). Places missing from these sources cannot be generated, and well-documented places may be systematically preferred. Though this bias can be mitigated by including additional resources (e.g. GeoNames) there will always be areas poorly covered by these auxiliary datasets.

Second, LLM bias inheritance and stylistic skew: generated texts may reflect stereotypes, bi-

ases, or dominant linguistic patterns embedded in the LLM’s training data. This can reinforce the ‘silicon gaze’ (Kerche, Zook, and Graham 2026) of LLMs in downstream models. Even when grounded, the way places are described can become homogenized (e.g., repetitive constructions, limited pragmatic contexts).

Third, methodological bias toward certain resolution heuristics: if generation explicitly inserts nearby ‘neighbor’ places to ground the text spatially, the resulting corpus may privilege geoparsers that exploit proximity-based assumptions (e.g., spatial minimality), potentially overstating real-world performance gains for those approaches. Similarly, an overrepresentation of highly populated places would favor geoparsers relying on population heuristics for toponym disambiguation, further skewing evaluation results.

Fourth, synthetic corpora may contain geographic or factual inaccuracies, introduced through model hallucinations. Models may produce implausible or incorrect spatial information during text generation, despite grounding generation in auxiliary context (e.g., ‘Leeds is south of Sheffield’). This risk is especially relevant when models attempt to infer spatial context beyond information available in their training data. Incorporating a GIS-based validation could help mitigate these inaccuracies.

Finally, evaluation bias could occur when the same model is used for both generation and geoparsing of the synthetic corpus, leading to better recognition performances of the specific model due to linguistic patterns created in the generation process.

5. Key research challenges

There are many research challenges the curation of synthetic corpora for geoparsing faces.

First, synthetic corpora rely on contextual sources like Wikipedia to ground texts, which introduces a source-coverage bias. Well-documented places are systematically preferred, while under-represented or less-documented locations are excluded. Finding ways to **reduce reliance on these auxiliary sources for contextual grounding** remains a key challenge.

Second, another major challenge in geoparsing is the extraction of complex location descriptions (e.g., ‘A9 between Graz and Leibnitz’) that extend beyond simple toponyms (Y. Hu et al. 2023). Generating synthetic corpora for these descriptions requires the **integration of spatial relationships (e.g., topological, directional, or distance-based) into the curation process.** However, LLMs often struggle to accurately represent spatial relationships (Ji et al. 2025), posing a significant hurdle for synthetic corpus generation.

Third, current synthetic corpora generation primarily relies on toponyms sampled from gazetteers, but texts often contain non-toponym spatial descriptions (e.g., ‘museum’, ‘stadium’, ‘school’). These descriptions require contextual disambiguation and linking to specific locations (e.g., ‘MoMA, New York’ from ‘a museum focusing on modern arts’). **Automating the annotation, disambiguation, and geocoding of such non-toponym spatial descriptions** is a critical challenge, as their interpretation heavily depends on the context provided during generation.

Fourth, more quantitative evidence is needed to showcase that the benefits of synthetic corpora outweigh the risks. In other words, the introduction of synthetic corpora for training and/or evaluating geoparsers should lead to measurable performance improvements in real-world tasks. These efforts will likely illuminate when and where synthetic data is appropriate and the degree to which it can supplement manually sourced texts.

Finally, ensuring the scalability of synthetic corpora generation computationally, linguistically, and geographically, remain a major challenge. Key obstacles include the limited linguistic and regional coverage of auxiliary datasets, language-specific complexities, such as conjugation in Finnic or Slavic languages, which complicate automated toponym annotation and uneven LLM support for languages with stark variations in text generation quality across linguistic groups.

6. Conclusion

Synthetic corpora are best viewed not as replacements for human-authored benchmarks, but as scalable, controllable complements. Grounded in gazetteers and real contextual descriptions, they allow faster corpus construction and let researchers control which regions, languages, and place types are represented. The open question is how much stylistic and geographic control we can impose before generated text stops resembling the texts geoparsers will see in deployment. Getting this balance right will determine whether synthetic corpora become useful for geoparsing research, particularly outside English-speaking and European contexts.

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Generative Artificial Intelligence Disclaimer

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT-5.2 for (1) Paraphrasing and rewording, (2) Improving writing style, and (3) Grammar and spelling check. The authors take full responsibility for this publication's content.

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